

Assessment of the Prevalence of Tuberculosis among Healthcare Workers in Kaduna State, Nigeria: Strategy to Inform National Tuberculosis Control Program

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Abstract

Healthcare workers (HCWs) are at increase rate of developing active tuberculosis than the general populations, more particularly these of the high TB burden counties with limited resources on infectious prevention and control measures. **Methods:** A retrospective cohort study was used to assess the prevalence of tuberculosis among healthcare workers from 2006-2020 in Kaduna State. 36 Health facilities were selected using a multistage sampling procedure. Tuberculosis (TB) central register was reviewed and data on related variables were collected using a checklist. **Result:** Of the 6325 confirmed active TB cases 10 were documented among healthcare workers. Out of which 02 were TB/HIV coinfecting and 03 were satisfied death. **Conclusion:** The prevalence of TB among HCWs in Kaduna State is very low while the death due to TB among HCWs is high in the state. **Recommendation:** A prospective cohort study should be conducted to document the actual prevalence of Tuberculosis among healthcare workers. The reporting system and proper documentation of TB in healthcare workers should be strengthening.

Keywords: Tuberculosis, Prevalence, Death due to Tuberculosis and Nosocomial Transmission

1. INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis (TB) is a major cause of death and disability in the world, particularly among healthcare workers (HCWs) (Sharma, *et al.*, 2018). TB germs spread when an infected pulmonary patient sneeze or cough around vulnerable TB group with low immunity (FMoH TB Training Manual 2020). The burden of the disease is high in Middle-income countries such as Nigeria due to high burden of HIV, poverty, unhealthy life style, poor early TB screening and prompt treatment with recommended valid anti-TB drugs (Kuyinu, *et al.*, 2019). Transmission of tuberculosis is more common among Direct Observe Treatment Short Course (DOTs) centers with poor tuberculosis infectious control (TBIC). (Kuyinu *et al.*, 2019). Despite the WHO ability to develop guideline for control and preventions of TB in healthcare facilities providing TB care services through DOTs, the implementation of these guidelines remains very low in low- and middle-income countries (Guo, *et al.* 2021). Globally, several factors have been associated with the developing of active TB among frontline HCWs. These factors include the negligence of health care workers to seek for medical care, poor working conditions, lack of personal protective equipment (PPE) both in terms of provision and utilizations, fear of stigma, poor supervision/surveillance, medical conditions such as cancer and diabetes mellitus and other risky life style like alcoholism (Shiferaw, *et al.*, 2021). As documented in literature, HCWs infected with pulmonary tuberculosis (PTB) stand more chance to infecting non-TB patients than the general population while discharging professional responsibility of patients' care (Di Bella *et al.*, 2019). A study in Italy confirmed that a pediatrician with PTB infected about 15 adults and 9 children within nine months in 2017 (Di Bella, *et al.*, 2019). Also, HCWs are at greater risks of developing not only drugs susceptible tuberculosis (DSTB) but including multi-drugs resistance tuberculosis (MDR-TB) and drugs-resistance tuberculosis (XDR-TB) as the result of prolong contact with TB patients.

Despite the fact that the transmission of TB to HCWs has been recognized as an occupational transmission since 1950s, evidence for TB transmission among HCWs in low and intermediate-incidence countries remain inconclusive due to the limited number of studies conducted on this regard (Grobler, *et al.*, 2016). Whereas, the outbreak of Covid-19 pandemic has increased the risks of TB infection especially

among health care workers due to total deviations from its care to Covid-19 response (WHO 2020). Tuberculosis is an opportunistic infectious disease that is curable and preventable provided all measures are put in place according to the recommendations of END-TB strategies (Orcau, *et al.*, 2011). The availability of healthcare services and effective training on infectious control is the backbone to limiting tuberculosis infectivity and mortality among healthcare workers (Oluwasanu, *et al.*, 2020). For planning of effective training, documentation of the recent prevalence of TB among HCWs is most important. Thus, this study aimed to assess the prevalence of TB among health care workers in Kaduna State, Nigeria.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Area and Design

Kaduna State is located at the north-western geopolitical zone in Nigeria, with a total coverage area of 46,053 square kilometers. The state has a projected population of 8,397,541 across the 23 LGA in 2017 with an increased to 3.0% of 6,113,503 of 2006 National projection (NBS, 2017). Agricultural activities are the major source of income in the state. A retrospective review of tuberculosis central register was conducted and elicits information on the number of confirmed TB case among healthcare workers from 2006-2020 in Kaduna State.

2.2 Study Population and Sampling Procedure

A Multistage convenient sampling procedure was used to select the study participants. At the first stage, all Local Government Area (LGAs) providing TB care services through directly observed treatment short course (DOTs) were selected. The second stage stratified the local government according to the three geo political zones. The third stage selected 2 LGAs from each of the geological zones, and 36 facilities were selected across all the LGAs using a convenient sampling procedure due to insecurity. Thereafter, all healthcare workers providing TB care services in both the public and private health facilities from the selected facilities were recruited for this study. For the interest of these study healthcare workers includes DOTs officers, Clinicians, community health, Laboratory staff, medical record, Nurses etc. Only healthcare workers with a valid documented record of active TB case from the TB central register are included in the study.

2.3 Study Variables and Sampling Methods

A checklist was used to collect a secondary data from the TB central register on the previous record of tuberculosis among HCWs from 2012-2020. The instrument contained information on facility name, LGA, Sex, Cadre, year, confirm TB case, TB/HIV, cured due to TB, death due to TB, TB in HCWs, TB cured in HCWs and TB death in HCWs.

2.4 Data Collection and management

Data was collected from the TB central register using a checklist on the burden of active tuberculosis among HCWs by the principal researcher. All data collected was validated through data triangulations method and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 23.0) Software. All information was presented in tables and fig to presents the outcome of the study result.

2.4.1 Ethical Issues

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Kaduna State Ministry of Health Research Ethics Committee and Health Research Ethics Committee of the National Tuberculosis and Leprosy Training Center (HREC, NTBLTC). All data collected was managed under high level of confidentiality and strictly used for the purpose of this study (NHREC/17/03/2018, LCU/REC/22/103/, NTBLTC/REC/21/016)

3. RESULT

Table 01: Demographical Distribution of active TB cases among HCWs by sex and cadre

	Confirmed TB cases	Death Due to TB	Cured
Sex			
Male	6 (60%)	2 (20%)	4 (40%)
Female	4 (40%)	1 (10%)	3 (30%)
Cadre			
Community Health	6 (60%)	2 (20%)	4 (40%)
Health Attendant	1 (10%)	1 (10%)	0 (0%)
Nurses	2(20%)	0 (0%)	2 (20%)
Lab scientist	1(10%)	0 (0%)	1 (10%)

This result shows that out of 10 (100%) confirmed TB cases among HCWs, 6 (60%) cases were diagnosed among male HCWs while 4 (40%) cases were among females. Majority of the cases 6 (60%) were confirmed among community healthcare workers. Out of the 3 (30%) cases that were satisfied death, 2 (20%) were community healthcare workers.

Table: 02 Occurrences of Tuberculosis per Year

Year	2012	2015	2016	2017	2018	2020	Total
Total Confirmed cases	414	574	556	799	738	880	3961
Confirmed cases (HCWs)	3	1	1	2	2	1	10

This result shows that 3 active TB cases were reported in 2012, 2 cases in 2017 and 2018 while 1 case in 2015, 2016 and 2020 respectively. This is to show that there are no documented cases of tuberculosis among healthcare workers from 2006-2011.

Table 03: TB Record in Kaduna State from 2006-2020

Total Number of Confirmed TB Case in General Population	6325
Cured in General Population	5811
Death in General Population	481
Lost to follow up in General Population	33
TB/HIV Co-infection in General Population	362
Total Number of TB in HCWs	10
TB/ HIV in HCWs	2
TB Cured in HCWs	7
TB Death in HCWs	3

This shows that 6325 TB cases were documented among general population from 2006-2020, 5811 were declared cured, 481 were satisfied death, 33 were lost to follow up, 362 were TB/HIV co-infected, 10 cases were reported among HCWs, 2 cases were TB/HIV co-infected among TB in healthcare workers, 7 were declared cured and 3 cases were satisfied death.

TB Record in Kaduna State from 2006-2020

This shows that 6325 TB cases was recorded among the general population from 2006-2020, only 10 cases were documented among HCWs out of which 07 cases were declared cured and 03 were certified death.

4. DISCUSSION

This study found that the prevalence of TB among HCWs was 0.158%. This finding is lower compared to other studies conducted among HCWs. For instance, a study conducted in Egypt reported that the prevalence of TB among HCWs was 0.5% (Amani and Sabri, 2015). Another study in Uganda documented about 1.7% prevalence rate of TB among HCWs (Kayanja *et al.*, 2005). Similarly, a huge 27.8% prevalence of TB was reported among HCWs in South Africa (Grobler *et al.*, 2016). In Nigeria, a study reported that the prevalence of active TB among HCWs was 1.5% with over 6% TB-specific-death rate (Salami, *et al.* 2007). Another study conducted in 2011 documented 3.3% and 2.2 % in the prevalence rate of TB among HCWs by Acid fast Bacillus (AFB) and Culture respectively in Nigeria (Kehinde *et al.*, 2011). The lower prevalence found in this study could be due to poor documentation associated with health sectors in Nigeria. However, this finding is relevant because, no known recent study has reported the prevalence of active TB among HCWs in Nigeria.

This study had also documented that 3 cases out of the 10 confirmed cases among HCWs were satisfied death; this shows that the death due to TB among HCWs is 30%. This finding is higher than a study that reported 6.3% death rate due to TB among HCWs in Nigeria (Salami, et al. 2007). A study conducted in South Africa on the outcome of TB among HCWs has reported 0.0% death rate of TB among HCWs (Idongesit *et al.*, 2009). Another study has also reported 0.0% death rate due to TB in Taiwan (Pan et al, 2015). These differences were due to the facts that from the finding of these studies none of the confirmed HCWs has TB/HIV co-infection while all the Nigerian study has reported TB/HIV co-infection.

4.1 Limitation of the Study

The limitations of this research study are related to the inherent limitation of all retrospective cohort study design and use of secondary data, which includes challenges with data quality and poor/improper documentation that are more likely to affect the study.

4.2 Conclusion and Recommendation

The prevalence of active tuberculosis among HCWs in Kaduna State is very low. The death rate among healthcare due to TB is high. To document the actual burden of TB among HCWs in Kaduna State, we recommended that a prospective study (clinical trial) should be conducted on the burden of active TB among healthcare workers in the state. Another recommendation is to strengthen the actual reporting and proper documentations of active TB among HCWs.

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Assessment on the Prevalence of Tuberculosis among Healthcare Workers in Kaduna
State, Nigeria: Strategy to Inform National Tuberculosis Control Program
Checklist for Data Collection

Local government.....

Facility Name.....

YEAR	CONFIRM TB CASE	TB/HIV	CURED	DEATH	TB IN HCWs	TB/HIV IN HCWs	TB CURED IN HCWs	TB DEATH IN HCWs	SEX	CADRE
2006										
2007										
2008										
2009										
2010										
2011										
2012										
2013										
2014										
2015										
2016										
2017										
2018										
2019										
2020										

MINISTRY OF HEALTH
KADUNA STATE, NIGERIA

MOH/ADM/744/VOL.1/ 1155

13TH DECEMBER, 2021

NHREC/17/03/2018'

NOTICE OF EXPEDITED REVIEW AND APPROVAL

**ASSESSMENT OF THE NOSOCOMIAL TRANSMISSION AND BURDEN OF TUBERCULOSIS WITH
ASSOCIATED RISK FACTORS AMONG HEALTH CARE WORKERS IN KADUNA STATE, NIGERIA:
STRATEGY TO INFORM POLICY**

Name of Principal Investigator : **CHIROMA LAMINU**
Address of Principal Investigator: **LEAD UNIVERSITY IBADAN,
OYO STATE.**

Date of receipt of Application : **13TH DECEMBER, 2021**
Date of Ethical Approval : **21ST DECEMBER, 2021**
Date of Expiry of Approval: **21ST DECEMBER, 2022**

This is to inform you that the Research described in the submitted Protocol, the Consent Forms, advertisements and other participant information have been reviewed and given Expedited approval by the the Health Research Ethics committee (HREC) of Kaduna State Ministry of Health.

If there is delay in starting the research or any need for correction, inform the HREC secretariat so that the dates of approval or other corrections can be effected accordingly.

However, Researcher is kindly requested to submit a copy of his/her findings to the State Ministry of Health, please

DR. SUNDAY JOSEPH
For: Chairman

Motto: Knowledge for Self-reliance
Lagos - Ibadan Expressway, Toll Gate Area, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria
Email: lcu.hr@lcu.edu.ng

University Research Ethics Committee

PROJECT TITLE: ASSESSMENT OF THE NOSOCOMIAL TRANSMISSION AND BURDEN OF TUBERCULOSIS WITH ASSOCIATED RISK FACTORS AMONG HEALTHCARE WORKERS IN KADUNA STATE, NIGERIA: STRATEGY TO INFORM POLICY.

PROJECT NUMBER: LCU-REC/22/103.

APPROVAL LETTER

The above named proposal has been adequately reviewed; the protocol and safety guidelines satisfy the conditions of LCU-REC policies regarding experiments that use human subjects.

Therefore, the study under its reviewed state is hereby approved by the LCU - Research Ethics Committee.

Prof. Otusola Ladokun
Name of LCU-REC Chairman *Signature of LCU-REC Chairman*

Dr. Folahanmi Akinsolu
Name of LCU-REC Secretary *Signature of LCU-REC Secretary*

This approval is given with the investigator's Declaration as stated below:

By signing below I agree/certify that:

1. I have reviewed this protocol submission in its entirety and that I am fully cognizant of, and in agreement with all submitted statements.
2. I will conduct this research study in strict accordance with all submitted statements except where a change may be necessary to eliminate apparent immediate hazard to a given research subject.
 - I will notify the REC promptly of any change in research procedures necessitated in the interest of the safety of a given research subject.
 - I will request and obtain REC approval of any proposed modification to the research protocol or informed consent document(s) prior to implementing such modifications.

FEDERAL MINISTRY OF HEALTH
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Your Ref: _____
HREC/NTBLTC/12-21/VL/2007
Our Ref: _____
20th December, 2021
Date: _____

The Head of Department,
Department of Public Health,
Lead City University, Ibadan,
Oyo State, Nigeria.

Letter of Ethical Approval
Attention: Chiroma Laminu

Your research proposal title "Assessment on the Burden of Tuberculosis with associated Risk Factors among Healthcare Workers in Kaduna State, Nigeria: Strategy to Inform Policy. This is to convey the approval for ethical clearance for the commencement of the research and the use of National Tuberculosis and Leprosy Training Center and Referral Hospital, Zaria for collection of Data.

You are required to notify the committee of the progress being made and any protocol amendment(s), serious unexpected outcome related to the conduct of this study or termination for any reason. Note that, you are expected to share the findings of this research with NTBLTC both in hard and soft copy upon completion.

The NTBLTC takes this opportunity to thank you for choosing this institution and wishes you the best in your endeavors.

Yours Faithfully

Dr. E.N. Iya,
Chairman
HREC

Author(s)

1

Chiroma Laminu

He has been a facilitator with National Tuberculosis and Leprosy Training Center Zaria for more than half decade. He is also the Managing Director and the founder of Idris Mika'il Collage of Public Health Rikochi, Kaduna State. He obtained Bachelor degree in public health from Cavendish University Uganda, Master degree in Disaster Management from Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Master degree in Health Economics, Master degree in Public Health all from Bayero University, Kano and PhD in Public Health epidemiology from Lead City University Ibadan respectively. His research focus is on the area of infectious diseases more particularly, Tuberculosis, Leprosy and HIV.

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